

Quantum Interference/Noninterference Interactions and their Statistics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 9, 2023

In classical statistical mechanics, although one has averages of a system, a single particle within the system has properties which are sharply defined at any x, t , even though these properties change stochastically, i.e. through interactions. A quantum free particle, on the other hand, has information based on the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, multiplied by i to create periodicity which indicates an inherent information, not one based on the outcome of trial runs or interactions. The probability is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If E and p are considered as constant, then there are independent probabilistic fluctuations in x and t , which means there may be corresponding probabilistic interactions, both impulse ones (one dimensional reflection/refraction, n -slits) and temporal ones (Rabi frequency). In such a case, one has interference and the form $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ governing the statistics, not a maximization of entropy linked to interaction/outcome results. Nevertheless, the quantum particle interacts with fields, it seems, which give rise to p or E changes. It seems the key idea is that one has stochastic uncertainty before an interaction occurs and hence interference.

The alternative is that such stochastic uncertainty does not exist before a specific interaction, i.e. the inherent probability $\exp(-iEt)$ or $\exp(ipx)$ has no effect on the interaction. This is not to say that there cannot be probabilities before the interaction. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, there are probabilities $P(e_1)$ and $P(e_2)$ for particles with e_1 and e_2 , but a specific e_1 and e_2 have no uncertainty. The uncertainty is in the outcome of the reaction.

Another example is a two state electron in an atom which absorbs and emits photons. The rules for time evolution are that the ground state is represented by $\exp(-iE_0t)$, but at some stochastic t value, it changes to $\exp(-iE_1t)$ and vice versa. The ground state absorbs a photon and the excited emits. The two states are clearly defined by the differing interactions which govern their time dependence which is taken to be simply the changing of E_0 to E_1 and vice versa. This problem is then based on probabilities based on outcomes of an interaction and maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is employed. There is no initial interference.

Statistical Mechanics and Probability Based on Outcomes of an Interaction

A coin or die is initially in a well-defined state. There is no inherent stochasticity. It is then tossed and the stochasticity enters through the interaction. The final state is also sharply defined, but since one does not know what it is, one assigns probabilities. As a result, one maximizes entropy subject to a constraint to show the possible interaction outcomes. We call a trial toss an interaction. Here the constraint is $\sum_i P(i)=1$.

For a particle in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, there are also sharply defined states, i.e. kinetic energy ones and particles collide at a sharp x at a sharp t . Maximization of entropy subject to $\sum_i P(e_i)$ leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor, which is an outcome based probability. Stochasticity occurs during an interaction. Even though there is a probability $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ for e_1 and e_2 to collide, a given single particle reaction deals with a definite e_1 and a

definite e^2 and these may exist at a definite x and t . Such does not seem to always be the case in quantum mechanics,

Quantum Free Particle and Intrinsic Probability

In general, information is defined as:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = \text{constant } e_i \quad ((1))$$

Here e_i is a sharp value and $P(e_i)$ is real. Furthermore, e_i is a property of the particle which changes in an interaction and it is the interaction which introduces stochasticity.

For a quantum free particle, information is the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ multiplied by i . $-Et+px$ also consists of sharp values, but i makes the probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ fuzzy in t and x , if E and p are considered to be constant (i.e. sharp). There is stochastic behaviour even before any interaction occurs. In fact, it is this stochastic uncertain behaviour which governs the stochasticity of the interaction. This behaviour removes sharp certainty before an interaction occurs, leading to a contrast with classical physics for which everything is sharply defined before an interaction. For example, consider a 2-slit. Classically a particle goes through one slit or the other because there is no uncertainty before the interaction. In the quantum case, there are fluctuations in space of the order of a wavelength \hbar/p . If two slits are separated by about a wavelength, the particle may interact with both and one has no idea which slit it passes through (even though it only passes through one). One has interfering probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ for each slit with the outcome moving towards a particular point on a screen. There is interference and no maximization of entropy subject to constraints for the outcomes (even though $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ may be argued to represent maximization of entropy subject to $ipxP(x)$ and $-iEtP(t)$ constraints).

The lack of certainty before an interaction leads to interference and OR sums of $\exp(ipx)$'s or $\exp(-iEt)$'s describing the interaction. Two other examples are a single bound state particle with a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, the wavefunction or OR probability sum is:

$$W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Each known p has stochasticity in x and this combines with $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ in a predictable manner i.e.

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x) \quad ((3))$$

The so-called stochasticity of interactions with $V(x)$ is given by the weights $a(p)$, but these are determined through an overall conservation of energy, so this is not free stochasticity from an interaction.

$$-1/2m \ d^2W/dx^2 / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ and conservation of energy are the two guiding principles.

A third example is one dimensional reflection/refraction of a photon at $x=0$ where an interface along the y axis separates n_1 and n_2 (indices of refraction). In such a case, $\exp(ipx)$ continuities and first derivative continuities define the statistical outcome because there is fuzziness before the interaction which allows for interference i.e.

$$A\exp(ipx)+B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((5a)) and } A\exp(ipx)-B\exp(-ipx)=Cp2\exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((5b))}$$

Again, as we have previously argued, the inherent $\exp(ipx)$ controls the stochasticity of the problem. Here we wish to point out one extra feature. It is possible to multiply ((5a)) and ((5b)) together to obtain: $AA/c=BB/c+CC/c^2$. If $AA=1$, one has the usual conservation of probability. Equation ((5a)) (not at $x=0$), however, should be linked to conservation of probability as well. If one multiplies ((5a)) by its complex conjugate (not just at $x=0$) one obtains:

$$AA + BB + AB2 \cos(px) \text{ for } x<0 \text{ and } CC \text{ for } x>0 \text{ ((6))}$$

One should be able to integrate over space, but this is a steady state problem. If one considers $x=ct$ for $x<0$ ($n_1=1$) and $x= c2t$ for $x>0$ ($c2=c/n2$), i.e. and notes that B moves in the negative x direction so one integrates from right to left for BB , (i.e. uses dx/c for AA , $-dx/c$ for BB and $dx/c2$ for CC) then $AB2 \cos(px)$ drops out and one has::

$AA/c-BB/c=CC/c^2$ which is again conservation of probability. Here A represents the incident photon, B the reflected and C the refracted. A similar result does not hold by multiplying ((5b)) by its complex conjugate because there is no associated conservation.

Rabi Frequency

A main example we wish to consider in this note is that of Rabi frequency. This represents an example involving $\exp(-iEt)$ which may also be fuzzy and allow for interference. If interference occurs, this means that one has $\exp(-iE_0t)W_0(x) + \exp(-iE_1t)W_1(x)$, for example. Even at $t=0$, fuzziness or uncertainty in E exists as one may E_0 or E_1 . These have different energies and the average energy changes in time. This suggests an interaction with a field which may receive or supply energy. We argue that an interaction occurs, but in a very special way, namely through the $\exp(-iEt)$ time dependence of energy eigenfunction states. There is no stochasticity associated with interactions as in classical physics, rather it is the energy eigenstate time dependence $\exp(-iEt)$ which prevail, but yields interactive results due to interference.

A specific example is a particle with spin .5 in the x direction which appears as:

$$|x \text{ spin } .5\rangle = \text{sqrt}(1/2) |z \text{ spin } .5\rangle + \text{sqrt}(1/2)|z \text{ spin } -.5\rangle \text{ ((7))}$$

If a magnetic field B_z is switched on (i.e. an interaction occurs) then $H= \text{constant} * B_z$ ((8)). As a result, the time dependence of ((7)) is:

$$W(t) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-iE_0t) |z \text{ spin } \uparrow\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-iE_1t) |z \text{ spin } \downarrow\rangle \quad ((8))$$

There is genuine uncertainty as to whether one has spin up or down ((7)) before the interaction starts (turning on B_z) and this persists after B_z is on. The system has an average energy changing in time, suggesting it receives and emits energy to the B_z field, but the time dependence is given by ((8)) and there is interference. One might argue that the particle is either in a spin up or spin down state and so there should be different specific interaction rules for each, but this is not the case. This situation is analogous to a 2-slit problem. One might say that the particle must go through one slit or another, so there should be no interference, but there is due to initial uncertainty prior to the interaction with no sharp x value. Here there is no sharp E value prior to the interaction and this leads to $\exp(-iEt)$ type interactions with the B field and interference. As a result, this is an interesting quantum statistical problem.

We next consider a very different case, namely that of a two state quantum electron -nucleus system interacting with photons.

Two State Quantum System Interacting with Photons

An electron bound to a nucleus may have two states E_0 and E_1 , governed by the time-independent Schrodinger equation, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and conservation of energy. These have time dependent factors $\exp(-iE_0t)$ and $\exp(-iE_1t)$. In general, one states that the system evolves in time according to its Hamiltonian. In the case of photons, however, there is a specific rule which governs the interactions and there is no uncertainty associated with these rules i.e.

E_1 the excited state must emit a photon of energy $E_1 - E_0$ at some stochastic time t ((9a))

E_0 the ground state must absorb a photon of energy $E_1 - E_0$ at some stochastic time ((9b))

From the point of view of the interaction, there is no uncertainty before an interaction as in the cases in the above section. Thus there is no interference. One treats E_0 and E_1 as certain states and the uncertainty (stochasticity) is related to the times at which absorption and emission occur. As a result, one no longer uses $\exp(-iEt)$ to solve this problem, but imagines $P(E_0)$, $P(E_1)$ and considers the maximization of entropy subject to $E_0P(E_0) + E_1P(E_1)$. As a result, the system interacts with a heat bath, i.e. the photons in a certain way that it has a temperature T . As a result, an extra parameter is needed which was not found in the Rabi frequency problem. This extra parameter is related to the interactions in the problem and is statistical. In the Rabi frequency problem, $\exp(-iEt)$ governs the statistics and no extra statistical parameter is needed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there seem to be two different types of statistics, one based on quantum $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-iEt)$ which introduces stochasticity in x and t (which would usually be sharp values). before an interaction occurs (and so governs the stochasticity of the interaction

through sum (OR) situations. The lack of sharpness before an interaction means there is interference.

The second is one for which there are sharp values before a specific interaction, but there is stochasticity associated with the reaction itself. This is the case of a specific reaction in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. A specific e_1 and e_2 collide, but one does not know what the product energies will be, other than $e_{\text{total}} = e_1 + e_2$. The stochasticity is in the interaction outcomes and so one maximizes entropy subject to a constraint. The sharpness before an interaction means there is no interference.